

FAIR^e-AI

Fostering Austria's Innovative strength and Research excellence in Artificial Intelligence

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Artificial
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Artificial Intelligence Mission Austria
Förderinitiative (Aim At)
Leitprojekt

FAIR-AI Science Mapping

Task 7.1
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Project Context

- **Artificial Intelligence Mission Austria Förderinitiative (Aim At)
Leitprojekt FAIR-AI**
- **Task 7.1 Mapping of Austrian AI R&D activities**
- **Challenging task known from previous projects:**
E.g. Künstliche Intelligenz als thematische Herausforderung für österreichische Universitäten,
Auftragsprojekt für das BMBWF, Sektion Universitäten und Fachhochschulen, 2019

WP7 - Trustworthy AI Awareness
& Community Building

Austrian AI R&D
Activities

R&D
Collaborations

Tasks:

- 7.1. Mapping of Austrian AI R&D activities
 - detailed characterization of Austrian R&D activities in the field of AI over the past three years
- 7.2. Stakeholder involvement
 - brings together all relevant stakeholder groups, future users
 - different perspectives and requirements in the FAIR-AI R&D process
- 7.3. Establish R&D Collaborations and Exchange
 - create a sustainable research collaboration within the Austrian AI community
 - promote technology leadership and excellence

Methods:

- Literature review, bibliometric analysis, expert judgment, synthesis & conceptualization
- Data identification, retrieval, and analysis with statistical methods and network analysis
- Using three databases: EUPRO database developed by AIT (EU framework programs); national funding data (FWF, FFG); WoS publication database;
- Co-creation process with multi-stakeholder-workshops
- forward-looking methodologies
- Quadruple helix (Q4) involvement
- Seminars and community workshops

Objective

This task provides a detailed characterization of Austrian R&D activities in the field of AI over the past five years.

Relevant AI topics and actors are identified in systematic R&D databases by using a keyword search, and their networking and thematic orientation in the context of AI is characterized.

Methods

- Literature review, bibliometric analysis, expert judgment, synthesis & conceptualization of search strategy, data identification, data retrieval, data analysis with statistical methods and network analysis based on various indicators.
- Three databases are used: First, the EUPRO database developed by AIT with systematic and adjusted information on research projects of the EU framework programs ; second, national project funding data (FWF, FFG); third, the WoS publication database.

AI Context

Defining AI

No general definition of AI

First born in 1956 (John McCarthy organized a six-week conference at Dartmouth College, USA)

Two types of AI: narrow und general AI (schwache und starke KI)

Broad definition by EC's High-Level Expert Group on AI (2018):

“Artificial intelligence (AI) systems are software (and possibly also hardware) systems designed by humans that, given a complex goal, act in the physical or digital dimension by perceiving their environment through data acquisition, interpreting the collected structured or unstructured data, reasoning on the knowledge, or processing the information, derived from this data and deciding the best action(s) to take to achieve the given goal. AI systems can either use symbolic rules or learn a numeric model, and they can also adapt their behaviour by analysing how the environment is affect-ed by their previous actions.”

Simplified AI system shown in a **natural human logic** of information processing and acting

Defining AI

Broad definition by EU Artificial Intelligence Act Article 3: Definitions (2024)

‘AI system’ means a machine-based system that is designed to operate with **varying levels of autonomy** and that **may exhibit adaptiveness** after deployment, and that, for explicit or implicit objectives, **infers**, from the input it receives, **how to generate outputs** such as predictions, content, recommendations, or decisions that can influence physical or virtual environments.

Waves of AI : Evolution of AI research

From classic programming (first wave) to data science and statistics (second wave) and to cognitive architectures (third wave)

Cognitive architectures must have the ability to learn autonomously in real time, to generalize, to reason abstractly and to use natural language

Currently, aspects of a fourth wave of AI can be found in the topics of Explainable AI (XAI), multimodality and context understanding, self-optimising and self-adapting systems, ethics and trustworthiness as well as collaborative and human-centred AI

Challenges, Approach & Methodology

Task 7.1 Mapping of Austrian AI R&D activities

Defining scope of the task

- Challenges - No generally valid definition of artificial intelligence (AI) - Research field with a multi-layered terminology - High number of specific keywords - High number of publications in Web of Science - Keywords alone not sufficient: Identification of AI subtopics necessary to consider content specializations
- Approach – Defining scope of AI in a systematic way (narrow/general; waves of AI; AI systems: sensing/perception, reasoning/decision making/learning, acting) - Selection of a representative set of keywords: Search in Web of Science for most frequent terms and their co-terms - Bibliometric analysis - Literature search for AI terminology - Expert judgement - Definition of AI research topics

Methodology

- Comparison of different approaches to define AI terminology
- Synthesis of identified literature, bibliometric analysis, expert opinions to define relevant keywords
- Relying on previous studies “AI knowledge map” by Francesco Corea was used to structure AI res. topics

Underlying systematics of chosen AI research topics

- Based on refined version of **AI knowledge map** by Francesco Corea (2018)
- **Refinement** by FAIR-AI experts (2024)
- Providing a systematics of AI methods (x-axis) including type of AI (line type), AI waves (colour), and AI problem domains in a natural human logic (y-axis)

AI research areas and terminology concept for data retrieval and analysis

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AI research topics

Search terms

knowledge representation and reasoning	knowledge graph* OR semantic web* OR automated reasoning* OR knowledge-based reasoning* OR semantic reasoning* OR semantic ai OR knowledge representation* OR knowledge reasoning* OR knowledge representation and reasoning* OR machine reasoning*
expert systems	expert system* OR fuzzy system* OR fuzzy logic
robotics	robotic*
natural language processing including large language models	natural language processing OR language understanding OR language generation OR machine translation OR speech recognition OR LLM OR large language model* OR Chat GPT OR OR GPT-4* OR GPT 4* OR *Claude* OR Yi-Large* OR Yi Large OR DeepSeek* OR Qwen* OR Mistral* OR openai
computer vision	computer vision OR activity recognition OR image recognition OR machine vision OR face recognition OR semantic segmentation* OR instance segmentation*
decision networks	decision network* OR bayesian network*
decision making and probabilistic models	automated decision* OR automated decision making* OR algorithmic decision* OR algorithmic decision support* OR predictive analysis* OR predictive analytic* OR prescriptive-analytic*
machine learning (general)	machine learning OR supervised learning OR reinforcement learning OR transfer learning OR federated learning OR unsupervised learning* OR *semi-supervised learning* OR *one-shot learning* OR few-shot learning* OR semi supervised learning* OR one shot learning* OR few shot learning* OR zero-shot learning OR ensemble learning OR t-sne OR random forest OR support vector machine
neural networks	neural network* OR deep learning OR generative adversarial network* OR variational autoencoder* OR graph neural network* OR LSTM OR Long Short Term Memory* OR xLSTM OR Mamba OR KAN OR Kolmogorov Arnold Network* OR RNN
autonomous systems	autonomous system* OR automated vehicle* OR connected vehicle* OR connected and automated vehicle* OR autonomous vehicle* OR *autonomous driving* OR automated driving*
distributed artificial intelligence	distributed artificial intelligence OR swarm intelligence or agent-based modelling or multi-agent system*
evolutionary algorithms	evolutionary algorithm* OR genetic algorithm*
artificial intelligence (general)	artificial intelligence OR AI * OR AI-* OR self-learning algorithm* OR self-learning system* OR self-learning model* OR intelligent system* OR cognitive computing
AI ethics	AI ethic* OR explainable AI OR * XAI *OR human-AI interaction OR human-centric AI OR deep fake OR deepfake OR *AI privacy* OR adversarial attack* OR recommender system* ¹ OR collaborative filtering* OR bias mitigation OR trustworthy AI OR fair AI OR responsible ai OR ai governance OR ai policy OR ai regulation OR ai-act OR bias detection OR algorithmic transparency OR ai fairness

¹ Remark: Ex-post experts' feedback recommended to remove „recommender systems“ and „collaborative filtering“ from AI ethics search string

Data retrieval

The listed keywords per subtopic were used to retrieve datasets per subtopics for

- Scientific publications in Clarivate's Web of Science (WOS) database
- European projects in AIT's EUPRO database
- National funded research projects (publicly available FFG, FWF projects data) in AIT's EUPRO database

Note: Organization names were taken as given by the databases. No manual standardization was conducted. Therefore, different names within the databases can occur.

For the search of scientific publications in the Web of Science (WOS) the Citation Cluster "4.61 Artificial Intelligence & Machine Learning" was added to the search

For the search of European projects the Field of Science (FOS) artificial intelligence, computational creativity, computational intelligence expert systems, heuristic programming, machine learning, deep learning, computer vision, robotic, natural language processing, semantic web, autonomous vehicle were added to the search

Data analysis

Retrieved data on scientific publications, EU projects, and Austrian national projects were statistically analyzed as follows:

- **Total numbers of scientific publications, EU projects, and Austrian national projects** per country, and subtopic → to get an overview of the involvement of important worldwide/European nations in the topic and subtopics
- **Their growth rates** total and within subtopics on various geographical scales (worldwide, China, USA, India, EU, Austria) → to capture the dynamics within the topic and subtopics and to identify recent hot topics
- **Comparison of topical specializations** of China, USA, India, EU, and Austria → to identify worldwide and European trends and topical strengths and potential for Austria
- **Collaboration structures** → to identify relevant collaboration networks on various scales (worldwide, European, and Austrian) and important Austrian actors and potential collaboration partners within academia and industry
- **Actors** → to identify highly relevant AI actors in Austria and Europe and involve them in FAIR-AI stakeholder process

Selected Results

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Retrieved dataset for quantitative analysis (scientific publications)

AI research areas	WOS documents		
	WoS documents 2019-12.08.2024 AUSTRIA	2019-12.08.2024 EU27 + UK, NO, CH, IS	2019-12.08.2024 worldwide
knowledge representation and reasoning	139	2.611	8.106
expert systems	92	4.463	18.921
robotics	596	21.356	61.907
natural language processing incl. LLM	216	7.654	26.378
computer vision	273	12.612	55.256
decision networks	44	2.386	7.815
decision making and probabilistic models	39	1.600	4.261
machine learning (general)	2.867	92.531	329.213
neural networks	2.194	83.917	386.383
autonomous systems	228	7.081	22.676
distributed artificial intelligence	62	2.919	12.342
evolutionary algorithms	193	11.524	56.393
artificial intelligence (general)	1.401	43.565	130.043
AI ethics	213	4.482	14.269
Citation Cluster 4.61 AI & ML	282	14.776	60.402
Total	6.468	227.270	880.013

Note: Identified publications rely on applied search within Web of Science data.

Retrieved dataset for quantitative analysis (funded projects)

AI research areas	European projects		FFG projects		FWF projects	
	(H2020, HEU) 2014-2024	(H2020, HEU) 2019-2024	2014-2024	2019-2024	2014-2024	2019-2024
knowledge representation and reasoning	128	81	28	22	16	5
expert systems	130	61	10	7	3	2
robotics	1419	790	60	44	18	15
natural language processing incl. LLM	250	155	17	14	8	6
computer vision	357	183	35	30	10	5
decision networks	10	6	0	0	1	0
decision making and probabilistic models	67	38	20	14	1	1
machine learning (general)	2121	1509	261	225	118	102
neural networks	912	655	116	105	34	28
autonomous systems	408	254	114	72	4	2
distributed artificial intelligence	98	66	12	9	5	4
evolutionary algorithms	29	11	0	0	1	1
artificial intelligence (general)	2863	2287	433	411	66	62
AI ethics	119	112	22	20	5	4
Total	6230	4229	806	673	226	181

Note: Identified projects rely on applied search within publicly available data on funded research projects.

Worldwide number of scientific publications per year and AI research area I

Worldwide number of Scientific Publications per year and AI research area II

Remark: AI & ML Citation Cluster was not regarded as specific AI research area

AI-related publications of European countries – absolute numbers (left), weighted according to research personnel (right)

Note: Data on research personnel retrieved from EUROSTAT, 2019-2022

AI-related activities of European countries within EU Projects – absolute numbers (left), weighted according to research personnel (right)

Note: Data on research personnel retrieved from EUROSTAT, 2019-2022; Cyprus was removed due to being a large outlier (right). © GeoNames, Microsoft, Open Places, OpenStreetMap, TomTom

WP7 – T7.1 Mapping of Austrian AI R&D activities

Identified Austrian AI-related research (absolute numbers)

WP7 – T7.1 Mapping of Austrian AI R&D activities

Worldwide AI specializations and Austrias specialization within Europe based on WOS publications 2019-dato (RCA-index)

China is specialized in

- distributed AI
- evolutionary algorithms

Europe is specialized in

- decision making and probabilistic models

Austria is highly specialized in

AI ethics*

knowledge representation and reasoning

USA is specialized in

- natural language processing incl. LLM
- decision making and probabilistic models

RCA = Revealed Comparative Advantage (this specialization index does not correspond to absolute numbers!)

* **Note: Ex-post experts' feedback recommended to remove „recommender systems“ and „collaborative filtering“ from AI ethics search string, which could reduce AI ethics specialization significantly.**

— PEOPLES R CHINA — USA — EUROPE — AUSTRIA - - - RCA=1

Worldwide AI specializations based on WOS publications 2019-dato

Austria, Europe and the USA have similar scientific AI profiles with specializations on
robotics
decision making and probabilistic models
autonomous systems

China has a different scientific profile, it is more specialized on
distributed AI
evolutionary algorithms
China is very underrepresented in decision making and probabilistic models and in robotics

Europe and especially Austria are specialized in
AI ethics*

Austria has also a specializations on
knowledge representation and reasoning (strong)
autonomous systems

USA is very specialized in the fast-growing topic
natural language processing incl. LLM

European AI specializations based on EU-Projects (2014-dato)

The **smaller** countries in terms of topic participation show the largest peaks in

AI ethics (Cyprus)

NLP incl. LLM (Czechia)

Decision making & prob. modelling (Luxembourg)

Austria is specialized in:

knowledge representation & reasoning (among top 2, closely following Ireland)

Autonomous systems (among top 3, following Finland and Sweden)

Greece, Finland and Switzerland are the **most specialized** large countries in **AI-projects**. Within AI related EU-projects they are specialized in:

Greece is specialized in:

knowledge representation and reasoning

AI ethics

Decision making & probabilistic models

Finland is specialized in:

Autonomous systems

Distributed AI

Decision making & probabilistic modelling

Switzerland is

specialized in:

Neural networks

Austrias specialization within Europe based on WOS publications (RCA-index)

Note: Results based on RCA = Revealed Comparative Advantage: this specialization index does not correspond to absolute numbers; * **Note: Ex-post experts' feedback recommended to remove „recommender systems“ and „collaborative filtering“ from AI ethics search string, which could reduce AI ethics specialization significantly.**

Main collaboration partners in AI-related EU projects with Austrian participation (from 2019)

Identification of

- Collaboration clusters on European level
- Network brokers (connecting clusters)
- Relevant potential European collaboration partners
- Additional Austrian actors for the stakeholder workshop series of task 7.2 (esp. Austrian companies)

Remark: Only organisations who have at least 5 collaborations with another organisation (edge weight=5) are shown. Size of node is based on the number of collaborations in. Red nodes show organisations which are based in Austria. If an organisation has at least one participating subsidiary in Austria it is also marked in red.

Main AI-actors in FFG-& FWF AI-related projects (from 2019)

- Identification of
- Collaboration clusters on Austrian national level
 - Austrian network brokers (connecting clusters)
 - Relevant potential Austrian collaboration partners
 - Additional Austrian actors for the stakeholder workshop series of task 7.2, esp. Austrian companies

Remark: Only organisations who have at least 3 collaborations with another organisation (edge weight=3) are shown. Size of node is based on the number of collaborations, i.e. degree. Color is based on the organization type.

Most visible actors within Austrian AI-related publications (left) and EU projects (right)

Organisations	Articles
MEDICAL UNIVERSITY OF VIENNA	926
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAT WIEN	836
UNIVERSITY OF VIENNA	692
GRAZ UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY	465
JOHANNES KEPLER UNIVERSITY LINZ	453
UNIVERSITY OF INNSBRUCK	388
HELMHOLTZ ASSOCIATION	355
MEDICAL UNIVERSITY OF GRAZ	342
UNIVERSITY OF LONDON	265
BOKU UNIVERSITY	260
CNRS	238
UNIVERSITY OF CALIFORNIA SYSTEM	221
UNIVERSITE PARIS CITE	220
SALZBURG UNIVERSITY	210
SWISS FEDERAL INSTITUTES OF TECHNOLOGY	198
TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF MUNICH	198
UNIVERSITY OF KLAGENFURT	186
HARVARD UNIVERSITY	183
UNIVERSITY OF MUNICH	182
MEDICAL UNIVERSITY OF INNSBRUCK	181

Organisations	Proj. (>30)
Fraunhofer Society for the advancement of applied research	88
Vienna University of Technology	51
Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique	49
Centre For Research And Technology Hellas	46
AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH	45
National Research Council	44
Commissariat à l'énergie atomique et aux énergies alternatives	43
University of Vienna	41
Delft University of Technology	39
KU Leuven	38
German Aerospace Center	37
VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd	35
Politecnico di Milano	32
VIRTUAL VEHICLE RESEARCH GMBH	31

Remark: Organization names as from the databases, not standardized manually.

Most visible actors within Austrian AI-related FFG & FWF Projects (from 2019)

Organisations	FFG-Proj. (>20)	Organisations	FWF-Proj. (>4)
ait.ac.at	112	tuwien.ac.at	34
tugraz.at	96	univie.ac.at	23
tuwien.ac.at	93	oeaw.ac.at	13
joanneum.at	68	uibk.ac.at	12
fh-ooe.at	34	jku.at	11
v2c2.at	31	meduniwien.ac.at	11
jku.at	28	tugraz.at	10
univie.ac.at	28	uni-graz.at	9
unileoben.ac.at	26	uni-klu.ac.at	6
avl.com	24	meduni-graz.at	6
fraunhofer.at	23	ofai.at	4
scch.at	23	ait.ac.at	4
uni-graz.at	22	i-med.ac.at	4
siemens.com	22	dieangewandte.at	4
bundesheer.at	22		
uni-salzburg.at	21		
uibk.ac.at	20		

Remark: Organization names as from the databases, not standardized manually.

Outlook & Impact

- AIT (FAIR-AI Task 7.1) presented and delivered the methodological concept for the search strategy of AI research areas and terminology to Austrian funding agencies and ministries for the development of the Austrian AI Monitor on Oct. 3rd
- Selected results of Task 7.1 will be considered to be integrated into the Austrian AI Monitor for continuous monitoring of AI research
- Possible R&D indicators or diagrams for Austrian AI Monitor

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Outlook: Possible R&D indicators or diagrams for Austrian AI Monitor

- Scientific research – output and thematical overview:
 - Number of scientific AT publications within AI (time dynamics) total and
 - Per AI research topic (per year shows increase or decrease of involvement)
 - Topical specializations within Austria/Europe/world
 - (Citation rates may be too specific)
- Applied research (funded projects):
 - Number of nationally/EU funded projects (time dynamics) total and
 - Per AI research topic (per year shows increase or decrease of involvement)
 - Topical specializations within Austria/Europe/world
- Collaboration visualizations

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